

AR-Eye: A Custom, Low-Cost Eye Tracker for Mental Fatigue Detection with Pattern-Based Machine Learning on Augmented Reality Headsets

Alexios Stavroulakis¹, Michail Roumeliotis¹, Ioannis Safranoglou¹, George Ramiotis¹ and Katerina Mania¹

¹School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Chania, Greece

Abstract

We present a low-cost, custom-built eye tracking system designed as a modular add-on for augmented reality (AR) headsets that either lack native eye tracking capabilities or provide insufficient ocular data for cognitive monitoring. Our system leverages infrared-enabled cameras and machine learning techniques to extract oculometric features—pupil diameter, blink dynamics, and saccadic velocity—in real time, enabling reliable detection of user mental fatigue. Unlike commercial high-cost solutions or restricted APIs of built-in AR trackers, the proposed device provides direct access to raw eye metrics under diverse conditions. We implement an unsupervised clustering approach combined with supervised classifiers to estimate fatigue levels on a per-second basis, integrating both self-reports and objective eye tracking data. Results are streamed into the AR environment, where individual and team-wide fatigue states are visualized through intuitive holographic overlays. This collaborative monitoring framework enables users to track both their own and others' cognitive states, supporting adaptive interventions in shared AR tasks. The system demonstrates the feasibility of affordable, portable, and extensible ocular-based fatigue detection for enhancing performance, safety, and well-being in group-oriented AR applications.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → *Mixed / augmented reality; Collaborative interaction*; • **Hardware** → *Sensor devices and platforms*; • **Computer systems organization** → *Real-time systems*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Machine learning; Computer vision*;

1. Introduction

Mental fatigue is defined as a psychobiological state of tiredness caused by prolonged periods of performing demanding, cognitive-load-inducing activities, reducing efficiency in cognitive performance [Cra14] [TIW14]. In road transport, driver sleepiness and fatigue are important risk factors for motor vehicle crashes and related injuries [MNR19] [DCB*22]. In healthcare, elevated fatigue levels have been strongly linked to self-reported errors, potentially compromising the safety and outcomes of up to half of patients under care [WTH*09] [HTMvdM*19]. In workplace settings, fatigue reduces productivity by increasing vulnerability to distractions and attention lapses [CCTL19]. Similarly, excessive mental workload can undermine coordination and performance in team-based tasks [BLD*19]. In aviation, pilot fatigue—often stemming from extended duty hours and insufficient rest [Gaw16] [AEÅ06].

Given these consequences across high-stakes domains, reliable methods for detecting mental fatigue include heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability (HRV), electroencephalography (EEG), electrodermal activity (EDA), respiration monitoring, and skin temperature measurement. HRV reflects autonomic nervous system bal-

ance but requires several minutes of stable data, easily influenced by physical activity or environmental conditions [SZJ*22]. EEG offers high sensitivity to cognitive states but is intrusive, requiring electrodes or specialized headgear, and is often impractical outside laboratory settings [ZGZ*23]. EDA measures sympathetic arousal but is confounded by factors such as heat, stress, and movement [HP05]. Respiration rate varies with posture, speech, or emotional state reducing its specificity [VG96]. Skin temperature responds slowly and is environment-dependent [SSP*18].

Detecting mental fatigue based on eye tracking offers advantages. It is contactless, portable, and task-specific, easy to use [NSK21] and rich in multidimensional features such as pupil, saccade, and blink detection associated with mental fatigue [AAH*25]. Eye tracking solutions exist, differing in form factor, precision, and cost. High cost, high-accuracy infrared-based systems such as Tobii glasses X [Tob25], Pupil Labs Neon [Pup25] and EyeLink 3 [SR 25] are suited for laboratory and field studies, while webcam-based computer vision methods provide low-cost, accessible gaze estimation [YK21, HWP*24]. Embedded trackers in Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) headsets al-

low gaze monitoring during immersive experiences, for both interaction and cognitive state research [Ber24] [WCH*24].

Pupil size is a well-established eye metric linked to the autonomic nervous system [HH20] and to mental fatigue. Mental fatigue is often associated with a reduction in pupil diameter [MTO*24, HvdLBK15a, HvdLBK15b, HvdLB*16, HWvdLB15], in controlled lighting, since illumination strongly affects pupil size [BSD25]. Another eye related indicator of mental fatigue is blink frequency [MC15], defined as the number of blinks per second or per minute [HA17], cost typically increases with time-on-task and reflects a decrease in arousal [BGGM*18, DSMP*14, GJOZ15, ZMMO*18a]. Saccadic movements, defined as rapid ballistic shifts in eye fixation [Pur01], are closely associated with mental fatigue, especially through metrics derived from their dynamics. For example, saccadic peak velocity, the highest speed reached during a saccade, is a strong fatigue marker and tends to decrease with fatigue [DSRC*12, SDC*17, RLLC18]. Similarly, saccadic mean velocity is inversely related to mental fatigue, with lower values indicating higher fatigue levels [CAK*14, DSMC*16, YK18]

Eye tracking for mental fatigue detection has been explored across a wide range of sectors, demonstrating its versatility in safety-critical and everyday contexts. Studies span transportation [YHJ*24, DHUM11], aviation [PLM*25, YCY23, RCJV25], healthcare [DC18, LJB24, ASY*24], military and defense [SWG21], first responder contexts [XZY*25], industrial or office environments [KAAQ*24, SRN22], and maritime navigation [MLYH24], among others. These studies indicate that eye tracking enables effective fatigue detection, improving safety and performance in multiple domains.

Despite advances in fatigue detection, physiological measures are often intrusive, high-precision eye trackers remain costly, and AR devices lack sufficient integration. Existing studies are also domain-specific, underscoring the need for generalizable, gaze-based approaches that support real-time fatigue monitoring in AR environments. This paper introduces a low-cost, modular eye tracking add-on for AR headsets without adequate native tracking, enabling prediction of mental fatigue from ocular metrics using machine learning.

The specific contributions of this paper include:

- A low-cost, modular eye tracking device designed for AR glasses without built-in or accurate tracking, expanding the applicability of ocular-based cognitive monitoring, providing pupil diameter, saccadic speed, and blink data
- A clustering approach for mental fatigue detection using unsupervised algorithms, integrating both self-reported measures and eye tracking metrics
- An analysis of variations in eye gaze movements across varied tasks, forming the basis for pattern-based clustering methods in mental fatigue detection
- A machine learning framework using ocular metrics to estimate mental fatigue in real time, enabling adaptive support in AR collaboration environment.

2. Related Work

Commercial-grade systems such as Eye-Trac 7 have demonstrated that changes in saccade speed and pupil variability are strong indicators of fatigue across age groups [ZMMO*18b]. Additionally, high-performance binocular systems have demonstrated exceptional precision in psychophysical studies [IRHS21], particularly under strictly controlled laboratory conditions. Although these systems offer high accuracy and reliability, they remain bulky, power-hungry, and are not cost-effective for general deployment. Our embedded, IR-enabled solution captures similar metrics within a low-cost, compact form factor, supporting wearable monitoring and AR integration, when portability is important.

Alternative efforts toward accessible pupilometry include webcam-based tools like PupilSense [SWMD25], cost estimate pupil diameter from consumer cameras. However, reliance on visible light makes them highly sensitive to ambient conditions. Our design circumvents this limitation by combining a Pi NoIR camera with optical IR-pass filtering and IR LED illumination, ensuring robust measurements across environments.

Past work has shown the use of gaze and pupil metrics in cognitive workload evaluation, especially in gamified or simulation-based tasks [GPQ*24a]. Low-cost approaches have largely focused on non-wearable infrared gaze detection [ASY17], which generally includes only basic directional monitoring. By comparison, the proposed solution is designed optimally for wearability, providing full assessments of pupil diameter, saccadic speed, and blink dynamics, thereby making it applicable to both enclosed and dynamic scenarios. This aspect makes it easy to integrate into extended reality (XR) systems, where hardware minimization is essential. An examination of eye tracking within VR identifies a critical lack of modular, able to fit solutions for consumer-level headgear [AMF23]. Our platform is easy integrated into VR/AR systems that lack inherent eye tracking capabilities.

Several studies have labeled mental fatigue or drowsiness data using only self-report, without objective measures. For example, fatigue labels were derived from Brief Fatigue Inventory scores at multiple time points [TVR*21], Likert ratings after each eye typing trial [BBH21], repeated smooth-pursuit fatigue ratings [BRBH22], pre-/post-protocol questionnaires for video clips [WTX*24], or Karolinska Sleepiness Scale ranges [KC22]. Such labeling relies solely on subjective report, which are prone to bias and fail to capture rapid fluctuations in fatigue [KHIR*23]. In contrast, our approach combines self-report with eye tracking metrics in an unsupervised time-series clustering framework, and applies a weighted formula based on reliable ocular features to assign interpretable fatigue-level labels, enabling discovery of meaningful patterns while maintaining clear categorization [HVBL18].

Most prior eye tracking studies on mental fatigue have been conducted for a single cognitive task, such as the Psychomotor Vigilance Test (PVT) [HPG*10], a visual search paradigm [DSMC*13], or a continuous tracking task [USO*23]. While these approaches enable controlled analysis, they often produce task-specific oculometric patterns that limit generalizability. For example, working memory-intensive tasks tend to reveal fatigue through slower responses and reduced accuracy arising from limits in capacity, attention control, and retrieval processes [UFAV14]. In con-

trast, visual search tasks have shown that fatigue can be detected through both subjective reports of exhaustion and distinct neural activation patterns but such methods need to be investigated using a wider variety of tasks [RJW24]. To address this, our study employs four mental tasks targeting different cognitive domains: sustained attention (AX-Continuous Performance Test; [CBCSS99]), working memory (3-back task; [Kir58a]), visuospatial processing (mental rotation task; [SM71]), and selective visual attention (visual search task; [HW98]). This multi-task design combines self-reported fatigue measures with objective eye movement metrics and captures multi-pattern eye behaviors, providing a stronger foundation for models that generalize across contexts.

3. System Architecture & Implementation

3.1. Eye Tracking Hardware Implementation

The device is built around a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (Pi), which performs image acquisition, real-time processing, and H.264 encoding. Integrated 802.11ac Wi-Fi and Bluetooth 5.0 enable remote operation for data streaming, calibration, and headless configuration (e.g., via SSH or a lightweight web interface), as well as over-the-air software updates—useful in wearable/head-mounted deployments. Video is captured with a Raspberry Pi Camera v3 NoIR Wide (Sony IMX708) connected through a short flex extender for flexible placement (Fig. 1). Illumination is provided by a single 940 nm IR LED with a 150° emission angle, driven from a GPIO pin via pulse-width modulation (PWM) for adaptive brightness control. To reject visible light while transmitting the LED output, an 850 nm IR long-pass filter is mounted in front of the lens, appropriately cut to size. Eye safety is ensured by limiting radiant intensity to $<0.008 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, within the IEC 60825-1 Class 1 exposure limit of 0.01 W cm^{-2} [Int14].

Bill of Materials (BOM)		
Raspberry Pi 4 B 8GB		~ €90.00
Raspberry Pi Camera Module 3 Wide NoIR		~ €33.00
phoebe-g2009 52 mm 850nm Infrared IR Long Pass Filter		~ €13.00
200mm Sensor Extension Cable for Raspberry Pi Camera Module V2/V3		~ €12.00
SanDisk Ultra microSDXC 128GB		~ €10.00
YAGEO Carbon Film Resistors – Through Hole 120 Ω		~ €0.10
KINGBRIGHT KM-4457F3C IR transmitter		~ €1.00
18650 Lithium Battery Shield V3 1 SLOT		~ €5.00
Eizfan 18650 3.7 3100mah		~ €10.00
PC (≥ 4 cores, ≥ 8 GB RAM, ≥ 2 GB VRAM)		~ €600
Other charges (cables, etc.)		~ €5.00
Total without PC		~ €179.10
Total with PC		~ €779.10

Table 1: Bill of Materials

3.2. System Architecture

The proposed system architecture integrates multiple Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (Pi) devices, each paired with an AR headset, to capture and transmit video frames to a Frame Processing Unit (FPU). Incoming frames undergo a pipeline of image preprocessing operations before being passed through a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that estimates pupil area and blink probabilities. These outputs are further processed using algorithms that derive angular

distance, velocity, and acceleration from x–y coordinates, enabling frame-level labeling of saccades and other eye movement metrics. A sliding-window approach aggregates these features, then fed into a trained machine learning model to infer the user’s mental fatigue level on a per-second basis. The results, together with the device identifier, are published to a Kafka topic. The AR devices, then, retrieve the available data streams and by matching the identifiers, associate each mental fatigue estimation with the corresponding headset, enabling real-time visualization of each user’s cognitive state in AR.

Figure 1: Hardware schematic of the monitoring system

3.3. Frame Processing Unit (FPU)

Each Pi (attached to AR device) communicates with the Frame Processing Unit (FPU)(Fig. 2), a Python-based server by opening a socket and sending its unique device ID to it. After the server registers the ID, it establishes a dedicated TCP connection and the initial socket is closing. Using the Pi Camera, it captures 1920×1080 resolution at 50 Frames Per Second (FPS) and streams to the FPU over TCP/IP for real-time encoding and transmission. The server handles multiple simultaneous connections from different Pi based AR devices and, because IDs are submitted before streaming, reliably associates incoming frames with the corresponding device.

Figure 2: Frame Processing Unit

On the FPU, frames were converted to grayscale, cropped to 400×400 around the eye, resized to 128×128, and fed to the pre-trained U-net model [RFB15] (mDice = 84.0% and real-time efficiency 45.2 FPS, 0.2 GFLOPS, 0.03 M parameters) from MEYE app [M*21]. The model was trained on 11,897 manually annotated, 128×128 grayscale images of mouse and human eyes [MCV*21].

For each frame, it produced pupil and blink probability maps. Frames with blink probability > 0.8 (set by internal tests) are discarded. In the rest, pixels with pupil probability > 0.65 are thresholded to a binary mask. Using scikit-image’s regionprops, we keep

the largest connected component as the pupil. The mask is resized to the frame and refined with nearest-neighbor interpolation. The system monitors eye closure duration and if a blink lasts longer than 1.5 s, it is classified as a non-wear state. Data transmission to the server is then paused until eye is detected again.

Finally, the centroid of the resized mask was taken as the eye's gaze point, and the same mask was used to fit a circle to the pupil in the 400×400 cropped frame.

Figure 3: Left: Eye Frame cropped 400x400px, grayscaled & resized 128x128. Right: Probabilistic region on the pupil area

3.4. Pixel-to-degree Conversion

To derive angular metrics (saccades, fixations), pixel coordinates must be converted to degrees. Following [SGL*14], this is done by dividing the horizontal and vertical fields of view by their respective resolutions to obtain degree-per-pixel ratios, which are then multiplied by pixel displacements. However, with our high-resolution camera (1080p), the ratios were implausibly small, thus even large displacements produced unrealistically small angular changes. As a result, saccade velocities never exceeded angular thresholds. To address this, we implemented an individual geometric calibration procedure for each participant.

Five fixation targets were placed on a wall in a cross configuration at eye height, with one central and four peripheral targets at ± 5 cm horizontally and vertically from the center, at a viewing distance of $D = 65$ cm. The angular separation was computed by trigonometric equation $\Delta\theta = 2\arctan\left(\frac{\Delta X}{2D}\right)$. During calibration, participants fixated each target while pupil centroids were recorded. The pixel displacement between central and peripheral fixations (Δpx) was divided by the known angular separation to obtain the pixel-to-degree conversion factor $k = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta px}$. Participant-specific calibration yielded conversion factors in both horizontal and vertical directions, which were applied to all subsequent eye movement data to express gaze trajectories, velocities, and accelerations in degrees of visual angle.

3.5. Labeling

Following [SGL*14], eye movements were classified per frame using angular velocity, acceleration, and duration thresholds. Saccades were defined as movements exceeding $240^\circ/s$ velocity and $3000^\circ/s^2$ acceleration, and fixations as movements below these values. Duration constraints were applied during buffer processing, where at 50 FPS (20 ms/frame) saccades were confirmed only if ≤ 100 ms (≤ 5 frames) and fixations if ≥ 100 ms (≥ 5 frames). Flickers—artifacts with unrealistically high values (e.g., $>1000^\circ/s$ or $>100,000^\circ/s^2$)—were also detected and filtered. The buffer is triggered when a frame is provisionally labeled as fixation, saccade, or flicker, and runs until terminated by a blink, an out-of-threshold movement, or five consecutive fixations. Upon deactivation, flickers are interpolated, gaze features (angular distance, velocity, acceleration, coordinates) recalculated, and frames relabeled. Events are

reclassified by duration: saccades longer than five frames (≥ 100 ms at 50 FPS) and fixations shorter than five frames are labeled “other” and excluded. To allow interpolation when the buffer begins with a flicker, the last non-blink frame is stored and prepended, ensuring its angular metrics remain available.

3.6. Sliding Window

Eye tracking data were recorded at 50 FPS. Every 50 frames corresponding to 1 second of data were translated into eye movement data and sent to the 1-minute processing queue, which holds the most recent 3000 frames ($60\text{sec} \times 50\text{FPS}$). The system normally streams data directly; however, when the buffer process is triggered, three cases can occur: (1) if fewer than 50 rows of data are returned from the buffer (e.g., 30), the system waits for the remaining frames to arrive before forming a complete 1-second segment; (2) if exactly 50 rows are returned, they are immediately sent to the queue; and (3) if more than 50 rows are returned (e.g., 70), the first 50 are sent to the queue, while the remaining 20 are held until an additional 30 arrive to complete the next 50-frame segment. Once the queue reaches 3000 frames or more, the complete 1-minute window is passed for feature extraction. From each 1-minute window, we first computed the base oculomotor metrics: fixation count, saccade count, and blink count. Using these, we derived the following kinematic metrics: **mean pupil diameter**, the average pupil size across all frames; **mean fixation duration**, the average duration of fixations from fixation-labeled frames and their count; **mean saccade duration**, the average duration of saccades from saccade-labeled frames and their count; **peak saccade velocity**, the maximum angular velocity during saccades; **mean saccade velocity**, the average angular velocity across saccade frames; and **mean saccade amplitude**, the average angular distance moved per saccade frame. We adopted a sliding-window strategy to capture temporal dynamics of oculomotor behavior, as mental fatigue develops gradually and short-term fluctuations may be uninformative. The resulting feature vectors are input to a machine learning classifier for mental fatigue detection.

3.7. Server Implementation and Data Distribution

For real-time, multi-user AR monitoring, each headset opens a WebSocket to a Node.js middleware that handles device pairing, data routing, and FPU integration. In the AR app, users select their Pi ID, mapping each headset to its eye tracking Pi. Pis stream eye data to the FPU, whose ML model outputs per second fatigue levels (low/mild/moderate/severe). The FPU publishes predictions, with device ID and timestamp as JSON to a Kafka topic. The Node.js server subscribes clients and relays the stream so headsets can view all users' predictions, highlight their own (e.g., color-coded holograms), and display team aggregates in AR.

3.8. Augmented Reality Environment

The AR component was implemented on Microsoft HoloLens 2 which has its own built-in eye tracking system. However, its API exposes only gaze position (x,y pixels) and blink events, but not angular metrics or pupil diameter, due to privacy and calibration constraints. To overcome this limitation, we integrated our custom low-cost eye tracking add-on (Fig. 4), enabling access to raw data

(pupil size, blink frequency, saccadic metrics), preserving compatibility with the AR ecosystem.

Figure 4: a) Side view of Hololens with attached electronics. b) Prototype Top View

The user interface (UI) viewed via the Hololens 2 is designed for minimal intrusion, displaying fatigue data as holograms tied to the users field-of-view (FOV). Upon initialization, users interact with a holographic menu to select their Pi ID via the monitoring panel for pairing (Fig. 5a). Once connected, the interface renders personalized and team-wide visualizations: individual fatigue levels appear as color-coded badges, e.g., green for low, yellow for mild, red for severe, overlaid on the user’s FOV. Aggregated metrics, such as team average fatigue or individual fatigue states, are presented via a monitoring panel initiated via a hand menu, or dismissed via hand gestures and hand interactions (Fig. 5c). When a user enters a critical severe mental fatigue state, a prominent popup hologram appears in front of teammates’ views to notify them of the affected individual’s urgent cognitive situation, prompting immediate support or task reassignment (Fig. 5b). This setup facilitates proactive interventions, such as task reassignment prompts when fatigue thresholds are exceeded, thereby enhancing safety and performance in AR-augmented environments.

(a) Hand menu (b) Alert popup

(c) Monitoring Panel

Figure 5: UI components

4. Experimental Procedure

Eye videos were continuously recorded using a lightweight eye tracking system mounted on a 3D-printed frame (Fig. 6). Eight participants (5 men, 3 women; aged 18–36) took part, all well-rested and instructed to abstain from caffeine, alcohol, and strenuous activity beforehand. Prior to the main experiment, they completed a brief training session to familiarize themselves with the tests and

Figure 6: a) Adjustable 3D printed camera arm. b) Participant during the task battery

Figure 7: Task Battery for inducing mental fatigue

response requirements. Six participants completed the full protocol, while two discontinued after two sets.

The experiment assessed sustained attention, working memory, selective attention, and spatial reasoning using four tests: AX-CPT, N-BACK, Visual Search, and Mental Rotation (Fig. 7) [HJB23]. Each session comprised three sets, with all tests (≈10 min each) presented in counterbalanced order and separated by short self-paced breaks. After each test, participants completed the fatigue subscale of the Brunel Mood Scale (BRUMS) [TLF03, TLLK99], consisting of four items (exhausted, sleepy, tired, worn-out) rated on a 5-point Likert scale (0 = “Not at all” to 4 = “Extremely”). The mean of these items yielded a 1–4 fatigue score, chosen for its strong validity as a mental fatigue index and low participant burden.

- AX Continuous Performance Test (AX-CPT) [MSM09]: Each trial comprised four letters (cue, two distractors, probe). A response is correct only when the first letter was A (cue) and the last is X (probe), irrespective of the two intervening letters. Any other cue–probe pairing is a non-target.

Figure 8: AX-CPT, example target trial with correct response

- N-back test: A 3-back test [Kir58b] was used to assess working memory. Letters were presented sequentially at short intervals and participants have to identify whether the current letter matched the one shown three trials earlier (Fig. 9)
- Visual Search task: This test assessed selective attention. In each trial, 11 letters (L and/or T) were shown in random orientations, and participants identified whether a T was present among the Ls (Fig. 10).

Figure 9: N-Back test & correct responses

Figure 10: Visual Search test

- Mental Rotation test: This test assessed visuospatial processing. Participants judged whether pairs of 3D shapes, rotated at 0°, 50°, 100°, or 150° were identical or mirror images (Fig. 11).

Figure 11: Mental Rotation Test [GK15]

5. Data Processing and Clustering

5.1. Data Extraction

Per participant, eye video recordings from tasks generated raw per-frame data. A 2-hour session (around 270,000 frames), yielded about 270,000 rows of raw data, via the same real-time processing pipeline. Each frame was linked to its exact timestamp extracted from video metadata. The pipeline produced eye related metrics as byproducts, yielding frame-level variables (timeStamp, frameNumber, pupilSize, pupilCntrX, pupilCntrY, blinkProbability, angularDistance, angularVelocity, angularAcceleration, and label). Using the exported start and end timestamps of each test, relevant segments were isolated and data discarded outside or between tests utilizing the cKDTree structure. The frame-level variables for each test segment were processed using the sliding window method, producing the same higher-level features as in 3.6, with the test name (indicating the corresponding test). A separate data batch was generated for each 10-minute test, and each row in the batch was labeled with the self-reported mental fatigue score.

5.2. Visual Pattern – Data Merging

Raw x,y gaze coordinates from all participants were analyzed, restricted to one minute after onset through one minute before offset for each test block. Trimmed gaze samples were then pooled across participants for each test (AXCPT, NBack, Visual Search, Mental Rotation). Spatial distributions were visualized with log-scaled 2D histogram heatmaps, zoomed to the 5–95% quantile range of X and Y. To quantify dispersion, we computed the mean and standard

deviation of gaze positions per task, and overlaid ellipses corresponding to $2 \times \text{Std}$ centered at the mean. These metrics are summarized in the Table 2. The pooled heatmaps (Fig. 12) highlight task-specific dispersion patterns. Focused tests (AXCPT, NBack) exhibited compact high-density regions and smaller ellipses, indicating constrained gaze. In contrast, visual search and mental rotation tasks showed broader distributions and larger vertical dispersion, consistent with scanning and visuospatial manipulation. Pooling all tests would obscure these task-specific oculomotor signatures. Thus, AXCPT and NBack were combined as the Focus group. The Exploratory group was split into its two constituent trial types, reflecting both their distinct cognitive demands and the nature of the experimental tasks.

Task	Mean X	Mean Y	Std X	Std Y	N Points	Σ time (s)
AXCPT	171.8	220.8	50.9	31.6	3441	5063.4
NBack	168.2	222.8	40.6	24.9	3361	3176.2
Visual Search	174.3	220.8	39.8	27.9	3581	3490.7
Mental Rotation	173.3	220.8	40.9	28.9	3511	3688.0

Table 2: Pooled gaze dispersion statistics by task. Ellipse width/height and dispersion time are aggregated

5.3. Data Clustering

Clustering was performed with TICC [HVBL17], which partitions time series into groups with shared temporal structure. We set $K=4$ to mirror four mental-fatigue states and selected per-dataset parameters (Section 5.1) via BIC minimization [Sch78]. The resulting eye movement clusters exhibit distinct temporal patterns. Next, we interpret these clusters in relation to mental fatigue.

For each participant-dataset pair, we computed means and z-scores for seven eye movement metrics using literature-based fatigue directions [BH21]. The seven metrics that we retained are the peak saccade velocity ↓, ean saccade velocity ↓, Blink count ↑, Mean pupil diameter ↓, mean fixation duration ↓, mean saccade amplitude ↓ and mean saccade duration ↑ while excluding saccade count and fixation count due to the lack of strong evidence for stable effects [BH21]. For each cluster c in each dataset, we then computed the **NaiveScore** $_c = \sum_{j=1}^k s_j z_{c,j}$, where s_j is the sign as specified in the previous paragraph, k is the number of metrics and $z_{c,j}$ is the z-score for metric j of the cluster c . Clusters were relabeled 1–4 within each dataset by sorting naive fatigue scores in ascending order (1 = lowest naive score, 4 = highest naive score). We then combined the relabeled datasets into a single unified dataset.

We trained a **Linear Ridge Regression model** on the unified dataset, using the seven eye metrics as predictors and the relabeled cluster index as the target. After the training, we keep four coefficient which correspond to the four eye metrics as the most reliable ones for mental fatigue classification indicators: saccade amplitude, saccade peak velocity [BA22], blink count [BA22] and mean pupil diameter [AAH*25]. We drop mean saccade velocity and saccade duration because saccade kinematics follow the main sequence, a tight amplitude–velocity–duration coupling, so these add little beyond peak velocity and amplitude [HW06]. We also drop fixation coefficient because its direction varies strongly with task demands [GPQ*24b]. We L_1 -normalize the four coefficients, i.e., we rescale them so that $\sum_{i=1}^4 |w_i| = 1$ while preserving their

Figure 12: Gaze heatmaps for all participants for each task. A dashed ellipse ($2 \times \text{Std}$) centered at the mean indicates dispersion

signs. The resulting signed coefficients are referred as weight (Table:3). We use linear ridge regression (L2) so the learned coefficients map directly to our additive fatigue score. L2 controls coefficient magnitudes (avoids extremes) and preserves non-zero coefficients (unlike LASSO), yielding stable, interpretable weights. Continuing, we follow the same procedure as Paragraph 2 of Sub-section 5.3, but now we apply the four weights in the naive score equation by setting $k = 4$, substituting s_j with the corresponding weight w_j and replacing $z_{c,j}$ with the z-score associated with the same eye metric as the weight w_j . The resulting relabeled, unified dataset will be used to train our machine learning models.

Metric	Absolute Weight Value	Direction
Peak saccade velocity	0.2366	↓
Mean saccade amplitude	0.3720	↓
Blink count	0.1299	↑
Mean pupil diameter	0.2616	↓

Table 3: Oculomotor Weight Table

Figure 13: *t*-SNE projection of feature space showing the four ranked fatigue states (1 = lowest, 4 = highest)

5.4. Machine Learning Training

Based on the comparative results in Table 4, the KNN classifier was selected as the core model for integration into the real-time pipeline. Although XGBoost achieved the highest AUC, KNN provided the best overall balance across accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which makes it more suitable for deployment. For this reason, the performance of KNN was further examined using the confusion matrix and the overall ROC curve (Fig. 14). The confusion matrix shows that almost all samples were classified correctly, with only a very small number of misclassifications across the four

fatigue states. The ROC curve further confirms the robustness of the model, indicating excellent discriminative ability.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
Baseline	0.3469	—	—	—	—
KNN	0.9900	0.9900	0.9900	0.9900	0.9974
XGBoost	0.9894	0.9894	0.9894	0.9891	0.9987
SVM	0.9861	0.9861	0.9861	0.9861	0.9976

Table 4: Performance comparison table of ML models; best in bold

Figure 14: a) confusion matrix and b) ROC AUC curve

6. User Studies

6.1. Procedure

We conducted a user study with 11 participants: six male (aged 18 to 33) and five female (aged 22 to 55). Among the males, two had corrected-to-normal vision (one with prior eye tracking experience) and four had normal vision without experience. Among the females, three had corrected-to-normal vision and two had normal vision. None had prior eye tracking experience. Predicted fatigue levels ranging from 1 indicating low fatigue to 4 for severe fatigue, were generated once per second from eye tracking features using the KNN model. To align predictions with responses in the battery task, timestamps were matched using a cKDTree structure, identifying the nearest prediction for each question of the battery task. This enabled each question's reaction time, trial repetition and correctness to be associated with a corresponding fatigue estimate. The collected data were organized into four task-specific batches, independent of individual participants. Each batch contained data from one test (AX-CPT, N-back, mental rotation, or visual search) across all runs and participants. The assumption was that higher fatigue would be reflected in slower responses and reduced accuracy. Reduced accuracy was defined as a lower probability of a correct response on a given trial.

6.2. Results

To examine whether model-predicted fatigue levels were associated with task accuracy, we conducted logistic regression analyses, as the dependent variable (trial correctness) was binary (0 = incorrect, 1 = correct). This modeled the probability of a correct response as a function of categorical predictors. Predicted fatigue level (1-4, Level 1 reference) was the main predictor and separate models were fit for each of the four task batches (AX-CPT, N-back, Visual Search, Mental Rotation), with trial repetition as a control factor. For the AX-CPT task ($N = 2,288$), the overall model was significant but small in magnitude (McFadden's Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0105$, LLR $p = 0.045$) and no fatigue levels significantly predicted correctness relative to Level 1 (Level 2: OR = 0.815, $p = 0.352$, Level 3: OR = 1.451, $p = 0.079$, Level 4: OR = 0.457, $p = 0.121$). For the N-back task ($N = 578$), the model was significant (Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0291$, LLR $p = 0.0013$) predicted fatigue levels were not associated with correctness (Level 2: OR = 1.149, $p = 0.563$, Level 3: OR = 0.785, $p = 0.352$), whereas trial repetition showed clear practice effects (Block 2: OR = 1.968, $p = 0.0048$, Block 3: OR = 2.705, $p < 0.001$). In Visual Search ($N = 477$), the model was significant (Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0694$, LLR $p = 0.013$) and higher predicted fatigue was associated with better accuracy: Levels 2-4 showed greater odds of a correct response than Level 1 (Level 2: OR = 7.109, $p = 0.0021$, Level 3: OR = 19.047, $p = 0.0011$, Level 4: OR = 10.068, $p = 0.0003$). In the Mental Rotation task ($N = 452$), the overall model was not significant (Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0198$, LLR $p = 0.355$), with no evidence of association between fatigue estimates and correctness.

To analyze reaction time (RT), which is continuous data, we tested normality with the Shapiro-Wilk test across all batches. All were non-normal (AX-CPT $p = 1.44 \times 10^{-36}$, N-back $p = 1.10 \times 10^{-16}$, Visual Search $p = 2.79 \times 10^{-14}$, Mental Rotation $p = 1.41 \times 10^{-23}$). We therefore used Kruskal-Wallis tests to compare RT across predicted fatigue levels (1-4) within each batch. When the Kruskal-Wallis test was significant ($\alpha = .05$), we conducted Holm-corrected pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests and medians summarized effect direction. For the AX-CPT batch ($N = 2,288$), RT did not differ by fatigue level ($H = 4.68$, $p = 0.197$). For the N-back batch ($N = 578$), a significant, non-monotonic effect of fatigue level was observed ($H = 11.46$, $p = 0.00324$): RTs were slower at Level 2 (median = 0.774 s) than at Level 1 (0.668 s, $p_{\text{adj}} = 0.014$) and Level 3 (0.675 s, $p_{\text{adj}} = 0.0057$). For the Visual Search batch ($N = 477$), the Kruskal-Wallis test was not significant ($H = 4.06$, $p = 0.255$) and no post-hoc analyses were carried out. For the Mental Rotation batch ($N = 452$), the Kruskal-Wallis test reached significance ($H = 7.96$, $p = 0.0468$) but no pairwise comparison survived Holm correction. Medians suggested slightly slower RT at Level 4 (≈ 1.485 s) relative to the other levels (≈ 1.246 - 1.427 s).

Overall, accuracy did not vary with predicted fatigue, indicating no reliable detriment to correctness and in Visual Search it even improved at higher predicted levels, suggesting adaptive responding by participants. Reaction-time effects were task specific: AX-CPT and Visual Search showed no RT differences by level, whereas N-back showed a strong non-monotonic effect with Level 2 responses the slowest. Mental Rotation showed an omnibus difference with

out reliable pairwise contrasts. This non-monotonic pattern likely reflects arousal and engagement dynamics, with under-arousal at easier loads leading to slower responses, rather than a simple increase in RT with nominal task difficulty.

7. Discussion & Limitations

In situating our approach within existing AR eye tracking solutions, we note that Magic Leap 2 offers strong accuracy with a 400x400 eye camera at 90 FPS. Our standalone tracker captures 1080p at 50 FPS and, using a mini U-net pipeline, attains mDice = 84%. Unlike Magic Leap's headset integrated design, our device is decoupled from the HMD. While our eye tracking relies on a separate computer, this enables parallel connections to multiple units, supporting scalable and cost-efficient deployments. Achieving comparable parallel operation with Magic Leap 2 would require additional headsets and an external processor, substantially increasing per-participant cost.

This study has three main limitations. Firstly, it was evaluated only on HoloLens 2. Broader validation across additional AR devices is needed to assess generalizability and device-specific calibration. Next, the use of a single, controlled battery-task test to induce mental fatigue limits generalizability to real-world scenarios. Lastly, pupil tracking degrades for downward gaze—likely due to occlusions and viewing geometry—indicating a need for improved camera placement and/or model adaptation.

8. Conclusion & Future Work

The study demonstrates a low-cost, modular IR eye tracking add-on for AR headsets that extracts eye metrics and via clustering algorithm plus a KNN classifier, estimates mental fatigue once per second with real-time AR visualization. The KNN model provided the best deployment trade-off and showed near perfect cross-validated performance differentiating four fatigue states. In pilot testing, predicted fatigue mapped more reliably to slower reaction times than to accuracy, with effects varying by task, indicating the system captures meaningful cognitive-state fluctuations. Overall, the results validate affordable, real-time ocular-based fatigue monitoring for individual and team use.

In the future, the design could be adapted for varied AR devices without eye trackers. Incorporating metrics such as PERCLOS (PERcentage of eye CLOSure) may enhance predictive accuracy. Larger datasets with more participants will improve robustness and eye tracking data across varied mental tasks could capture broader behavioral patterns and improve generalizability. Finally, the system could be extended to detect other cognitive states, such as situational awareness and drowsiness.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the EU project CREXDATA under Horizon Europe agreement No. 101092749.

References

[AAH*25] ARNOLD L., ARYAL S., HONG B., NITHARSAN M., SHAH A., AHMED W., LILANI Z., SU W., PIAGGIO D.: A systematic literature review of eye-tracking and machine learning methods for improving

- productivity and reading abilities. *Applied Sciences* 15, 6 (2025). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/15/6/3308>, doi:10.3390/app15063308. 1, 6
- [AEÅ06] ANNE ERIKSEN C., ÅKERSTEDT T.: Aircrew fatigue in transatlantic morning and evening flights. *Chronobiology international* 23, 4 (2006), 843–858. 1
- [AMF23] ADHANOM I. B., MACNEILAGE P., FOLMER E.: Eye tracking in virtual reality: a broad review of applications and challenges. *Virtual Reality* 27, 2 (2023), 1481–1505. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-022-00738-z>, doi:10.1007/s10055-022-00738-z. 2
- [ASY17] ARBABI E., SHABANI M., YARIGHOLI A.: A low cost non-wearable gaze detection system based on infrared image processing. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.03717>, arXiv:1709.03717. 2
- [ASY*24] AHMADI N., SASANGO HAR F., YANG J., YU D., DANESH V., KLAHN S., MASUD F.: Quantifying workload and stress in intensive care unit nurses: Preliminary evaluation using continuous eye-tracking. *Human Factors* 66, 3 (2024), 714–728. PMID: 35511206. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00187208221085335>, arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1177/00187208221085335>, doi:10.1177/00187208221085335. 2
- [BA22] BACHURINA V., ARSALIDOU M.: Multiple levels of mental attentional demand modulate peak saccade velocity and blink rate. *Heliyon* 8, 1 (2022), e08826. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844022001141>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e08826>. 6
- [BBH21] BAFNA T., BÆKGAARD P., HANSEN J. P.: Mental fatigue prediction during eye-typing. *PLOS ONE* 16, 2 (Feb. 2021), e0246739. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0246739. 2
- [Ber24] BERKMAN M. I.: *Eye Tracking in Virtual Reality*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2024, pp. 681–688. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-23161-2_170, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-23161-2_170. 2
- [BGGM*18] BORRAGÁN G., GILSON M., GUERRERO-MOSQUERA C., DI RICCI E., SLAMA H., PEIGNEUX P.: Transcranial direct current stimulation does not counteract cognitive fatigue, but induces sleepiness and an inter-hemispheric shift in brain oxygenation. *Frontiers in Psychology Volume 9 - 2018* (2018). URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02351>, doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02351. 2
- [BH21] BAFNA T., HANSEN J. P.: Mental fatigue measurement using eye metrics: A systematic literature review. *Psychophysiology* 58, 6 (June 2021), e13828. PMID: 33825234. doi:10.1111/psyp.13828. 6
- [BLD*19] BANKS S., LANDON L., DORRIAN J., WAGGONER L., CENTOFANTI S., ROMA P., DONGEN H.: Effects of fatigue on teams and their role in 24/7 operations. *Sleep Medicine Reviews* 48 (09 2019), 101216. doi:10.1016/j.smrv.2019.101216. 1
- [BRBH22] BAFNA-RÜHRER T., BÆKGAARD P., HANSEN J. P.: Smooth-pursuit performance during eye-typing from memory indicates mental fatigue. *Journal of Eye Movement Research* 15, 4 (2022), 1–16. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1995-8692/15/4/25>, doi:10.16910/jemr.15.4.2. 2
- [BSD25] BELLIVEAU A. P., SOMANI A. N., DOSSANI R. H.: Pupillary light reflex. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing, Treasure Island (FL), Jan 2025. [Updated 2023 Jul 25]. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK537180/>. 2
- [CAK*14] CAZZOLI D., ANTONIADES C. A., KENNARD C., NYFFELER T., BASSETTI C. L., MÜRI R. M.: Eye movements discriminate fatigue due to chronotypical factors and time spent on task – a double dissociation. *PLOS ONE* 9, 1 (2014), e87146. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0087146>, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0087146. 2
- [CBCSS99] COHEN J. D., BARCH D. M., CARTER C., SERVANSCHREIBER D.: Context-processing deficits in schizophrenia: converging evidence from three theoretically motivated cognitive tasks. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology* 108, 1 (Feb. 1999), 120–133. doi:10.1037/0021-843X.108.1.120. 3
- [CCTL19] CALDWELL J. A., CALDWELL J. L., THOMPSON L. A., LIEBERMAN H. R.: Fatigue and its management in the workplace. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews* 96 (2019), 272–289. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0149763418305220>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2018.10.024>. 1
- [Cra14] CRAIK F. I.: Effects of distraction on memory and cognition: a commentary. *Frontiers in psychology* 5 (2014), 841. 1
- [DC18] DALVEREN G. G. M., CAGILTAY N. E.: Using eye-movement events to determine the mental workload of surgical residents. *Journal of Eye Movement Research* 11, 4 (2018), 10–16910. 2
- [DCB*22] DORRIAN J., CHAPMAN J., BOWDITCH L., BALFE N., NAWEED A.: A survey of train driver schedules, sleep, wellbeing, and driving performance in australia and new zealand. *Scientific Reports* 12 (03 2022). doi:10.1038/s41598-022-07627-0. 1
- [DHUM11] DONG Y., HU Z., UCHIMURA K., MURAYAMA N.: Driver inattention monitoring system for intelligent vehicles: A review. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 12, 2 (2011), 596–614. doi:10.1109/TITS.2010.2092770. 2
- [DSMC*13] DI STASI L., MCCAMY M., CATENA A., MACKNIK S., CAÑAS J., MARTINEZ-CONDE S.: Microsaccade and drift dynamics reflect mental fatigue during visual search. *Journal of Vision* 13 (07 2013), 1346–1346. doi:10.1167/13.9.1346. 2
- [DSMMC*16] DI STASI L., MCCAMY M., MARTINEZ-CONDE S., GAYLES E., HOARE C., FOSTER M., CATENA A., MACKNIK S.: Effects of long and short simulated flights on the saccadic eye movement velocity of aviators. *Physiology & Behavior* 153 (01 2016), 91–96. doi:10.1016/j.physbeh.2015.2
- [DSMP*14] DI STASI L., MCCAMY M., PANNASCH S., RENNER R., CATENA A., CAÑAS J., VELICHKOVSKY B., MARTINEZ-CONDE S.: Effects of driving time on microsaccadic dynamics. *Experimental brain research* 233 (11 2014). doi:10.1007/s00221-014-4139-y. 2
- [DSRC*12] DI STASI L., RENNER R., CATENA A., CAÑAS J., VELICHKOVSKY B., PANNASCH S.: Towards a driver fatigue test based on the saccadic main sequence: A partial validation by subjective report data. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 21 (04 2012), 122–133. doi:10.1016/j.trc.2011.07.002. 2
- [Gaw16] GAWRON V. J.: Summary of fatigue research for civilian and military pilots. *IIE Transactions on Occupational Ergonomics and Human Factors* 4, 1 (2016), 1–18. 1
- [GJOZ15] GERGELYFI M., JACOB B., OLIVIER E., ZÉNON A.: Dissociation between mental fatigue and motivational state during prolonged mental activity. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience Volume 9 - 2015* (2015). URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/behavioral-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnbeh.2015.00176>, doi:10.3389/fnbeh.2015.00176. 2
- [GK15] GANIS G., KIEVIT R. A.: A new set of three-dimensional shapes for investigating mental rotation processes: Validation data and stimulus set. *Journal of Open Psychology Data* (Mar 2015). 6
- [GPQ*24a] GORIN H., PATEL J., QIU Q., MERIANS A., ADAMOVICH S., FLUET G.: A review of the use of gaze and pupil metrics to assess mental workload in gamified and simulated sensorimotor tasks. *Sensors* 24, 6 (2024). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/24/6/1759>, doi:10.3390/s24061759. 2
- [GPQ*24b] GORIN H., PATEL J., QIU Q., MERIANS A., ADAMOVICH S., FLUET G.: A review of the use of gaze and pupil metrics to assess mental workload in gamified and simulated sensorimotor tasks. *Sensors* 24, 6 (Mar. 2024). URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24061759>, doi:10.3390/s24061759. 6

- [HA17] HOLMQVIST K., ANDERSSON R.: *Eye-tracking: A comprehensive guide to methods, paradigms and measures*. 11 2017. 2
- [HH20] HALL J. E., HALL M. E.: *Guyton and Hall Textbook of Medical Physiology E-Book: Guyton and Hall Textbook of Medical Physiology E-Book*. Elsevier Health Sciences, 2020. 2
- [HJB23] HASSAN E., JONES , BUCKINGHAM : A novel protocol to induce mental fatigue. *Behavior Research Methods* 56 (08 2023). doi: 10.3758/s13428-023-02191-5. 5
- [HP05] HEALEY J., PICARD R.: Detecting stress during real-world driving tasks using physiological sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 6, 2 (2005), 156–166. doi:10.1109/TITS.2005.848368. 1
- [HPG*10] HIRVONEN K., PUTTONEN S., GOULD K., KORPELA J., KOEFOED V. F., MÜLLER K.: Improving the saccade peak velocity measurement for detecting fatigue. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods* 187, 2 (2010), 199–206. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165027010000324>, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2010.01.010>. 2
- [HTMvdM*19] HUIZINGA C., TUMMERS F., MARANG-VAN DE MHEEN P., COHEN A., BOGT K.: A review of current approaches for evaluating impaired performance in around-the-clock medical professionals. *Sleep Medicine Reviews* 46 (04 2019). doi:10.1016/j.smrv.2019.04.007. 1
- [HVBL17] HALLAC D., VARE S., BOYD S., LESKOVEC J.: Toeplitz inverse covariance-based clustering of multivariate time series data. In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (New York, NY, USA, 2017), KDD '17, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 215–223. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3097983.3098060>, doi: 10.1145/3097983.3098060. 6
- [HVBL18] HALLAC D., VARE S., BOYD S., LESKOVEC J.: Toeplitz inverse covariance-based clustering of multivariate time series data, 2018. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.03161>, arXiv:1706.03161. 2
- [HvdLB*16] HOPSTAKEN J. F., VAN DER LINDEN D., BAKKER A. B., KOMPIER M. A. J., LEUNG Y. K.: Shifts in attention during mental fatigue: Evidence from subjective, behavioral, physiological, and eye-tracking data. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance* 42, 6 (2016), 878–889. doi:10.1037/xhp0000189. 2
- [HvdLBK15a] HOPSTAKEN J. F., VAN DER LINDEN D., BAKKER A. B., KOMPIER M. A. J.: A multifaceted investigation of the link between mental fatigue and task disengagement. *Psychophysiology* 52, 3 (2015), 305–315. doi:10.1111/psyp.12339. 2
- [HvdLBK15b] HOPSTAKEN J. F., VAN DER LINDEN D., BAKKER A. B., KOMPIER M. A. J.: The window of my eyes: Task disengagement and mental fatigue covary with pupil dynamics. *Biological Psychology* 110 (2015), 100–106. doi:10.1016/j.biopsycho.2015.06.013. 2
- [HW98] HOROWITZ T. S., WOLFE J. M.: Visual search has no memory. *Nature* 394, 6693 (1998), 575–577. 3
- [HW06] HARRIS C. M., WOLPERT D. M.: The main sequence of saccades optimizes speed-accuracy trade-off. *Biological Cybernetics* 95, 1 (July 2006), 21–29. Epub 2006-03-23. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00422-006-0064-x>, doi:10.1007/s00422-006-0064-x. 6
- [HWP*24] HUTT S., WONG A., PAPOUTSAKI A., BAKER R. S., GOLD J. I., MILLS C.: Webcam-based eye tracking to detect mind wandering and comprehension errors. *Behavior Research Methods* 56, 1 (2024), 1–17. 1
- [HWvdLB15] HOPSTAKEN J. F., WANMAKER S., VAN DER LINDEN D., BAKKER A. B.: Does dysphoria lead to divergent mental fatigue effects on a cognitive task? *PLoS ONE* 10, 6 (2015), e0130304. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0130304. 2
- [Int14] INTERNATIONAL ELECTROTECHNICAL COMMISSION: *IEC 60825-1: Safety of Laser Products — Part 1: Equipment Classification and Requirements*, 3.0 ed. International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, Switzerland, 2014. 3
- [IRHS21] IVANCHENKO D., RIFAI K., HAFED Z. M., SCHAEFFEL F.: A low-cost, high-performance video-based binocular eye tracker for psychophysical research. *Journal of Eye Movement Research* 14, 3 (2021), 1–21. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1995-8692/14/3/14>, doi:10.16910/jemr.14.3.3. 2
- [KAAQ*24] KOUNDAL N., ABDALHADI A., AL-QURAIISHI M. S., ELAMVAZUTHI I., MOOSAVI M. S., GUILLET C., MERIENNE F., SAAD N. M.: Effect of interruptions and cognitive demand on mental workload: A critical review. *IEEE Access* 12 (2024), 54405–54425. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3383142. 2
- [KC22] KAO I.-H., CHAN C.-Y.: Comparison of eye and face features on drowsiness analysis. *Sensors* 22, 17 (Aug. 2022), 6529. doi:10.3390/s22176529. 2
- [KHIR*23] KUNASEGARAN K., HUSSAIN ISMAIL A. M., RAMASAMY S., GNANOU J., CASZO B., CHEN P. L.: Understanding mental fatigue and its detection: a comparative analysis of assessments and tools. *PeerJ* 11 (08 2023), e15744. doi:10.7717/peerj.15744. 2
- [Kir58a] KIRCHNER W. K.: Age differences in short-term retention of rapidly changing information. *Journal of experimental psychology* 55, 4 (1958), 352. 3
- [Kir58b] KIRCHNER W. K.: Age differences in short-term retention of rapidly changing information. *Journal of Experimental Psychology* 55, 4 (1958), 352–358. doi:10.1037/h0043688. 5
- [LJRB24] LISANNE K., JONATHAN G., RAINER R., BERNHARD B.: Investigation of eye movement measures of mental workload in healthcare: Can pupil dilations reflect fatigue or overload when it comes to health information system use? *Applied Ergonomics* 114 (2024), 104150. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0003687023001886>, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2023.104150>. 2
- [M*21] MAZZIOTTI R., ET AL.: MEYE: Web App for Translational and Real-Time Pupillometry. *eNeuro* 8, 5 (Sept. 2021), ENEURO.0122–21.2021. doi:10.1523/ENEURO.0122–21.2021. 3
- [MC15] MARTINS R., CARVALHO J.: Eye blinking as an indicator of fatigue and mental load – a systematic review. doi:10.1201/b18042-48. 2
- [MCV*21] MAZZIOTTI R., CARRARA F., VIGLIONE A., LEONARDO L., LUCA L. V., ALESSANDRO B., GIULIA R., GIULIA S., GIUSEPPE A., TOMMASO P.: Human and Mouse Eyes for Pupil Semantic Segmentation, Feb. 2021. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4488164>, doi:10.5281/zenodo.4488164. 3
- [MLYH24] MA Y., LIU Q., YANG L., HE M.: Recognition of marine navigators' workload based on eye movement features using bridge simulation. *Safety Science* 178 (2024), 106607. 2
- [MNR19] MORADI A., NAZARI S. S. H., RAHMANI K.: Sleepiness and the risk of road traffic accidents: A systematic review and meta-analysis of previous studies. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour* 65 (2019), 620–629. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1369847817306290>, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2018.09.013>. 1
- [MSM09] MARCORA S., STAIANO W., MANNING V.: Mental fatigue impairs physical performance in humans. *Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985)* 106 (02 2009), 857–64. doi:10.1152/jappphysiol.91324.2008. 5
- [MTO*24] MATSUI T., TAKAHASHI S., OCHI G., YOSHITAKE S., FUNABASHI D., MATSUOKA H., KAGESAWA J., DOBASHI S., YOSHIMOTO H., SAKAIRI Y., TAKAGI H.: Cognitive decline with pupil constriction independent of subjective fatigue during prolonged esports across player expertise levels. *Computers in Human Behavior*

- 156 (2024), 108219. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747563224000876>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2024.108219>. 2
- [NSK21] NAM S., SONG H., KIM Y.: Research on contactless bi-signal measurement technology for improving social awareness of individuals with communication challenges. *Applied Sciences* 11, 11 (2021). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/11/11/5169>, doi:[10.3390/app11115169](https://doi.org/10.3390/app11115169). 1
- [PLM*25] PEI H., LI G., MA Y., GONG H., XU M., BAI Z.: A mental fatigue assessment method for pilots incorporating multiple ocular features. *Displays* 87 (2025), 102956. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0141938224003202>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.displa.2024.102956>. 2
- [Pup25] PUPIL LABS GMBH: Neon eye tracking system. <https://pupil-labs.com/products/neon>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-08-12. 1
- [Pur01] Types of eye movements and their functions. In *Neuroscience*, Purves D., Augustine G. J., Fitzpatrick D., Hall W. C., LaMantia A.-S., McNamara J. O., Williams L. S., (Eds.), 2 ed. Sinauer Associates, Sunderland, MA, 2001. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK10991/>. 2
- [RCJV25] RUSSO A., CARDOSO JUNIOR M., VILLANI E.: Eye-tracking analysis to assess the mental load of unmanned aerial system operators: systematic review and future directions. *The Aeronautical Journal* 129, 1333 (2025), 529–558. doi:[10.1017/aer.2024.122](https://doi.org/10.1017/aer.2024.122). 2
- [RFB15] RONNEBERGER O., FISCHER P., BROX T.: U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1505.04597* (2015). doi:[10.48550/arXiv.1505.04597](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1505.04597). 3
- [RJW24] RYU H., JU U., WALLRAVEN C.: Decoding visual fatigue in a visual search task selectively manipulated via myopia-correcting lenses. *Frontiers in Neuroscience Volume 18 - 2024* (2024). URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnins.2024.1307688>, doi:[10.3389/fnins.2024.1307688](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2024.1307688). 3
- [RLLC18] RENATA V., LI F., LEE C.-H., CHEN C.-H.: Investigation on the correlation between eye movement and reaction time under mental fatigue influence. In *2018 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW)* (2018), pp. 207–213. doi:[10.1109/CW.2018.00046](https://doi.org/10.1109/CW.2018.00046). 2
- [Sch78] SCHWARZ G.: Estimating the dimension of a model. *The Annals of Statistics* 6, 2 (1978), 461–464. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2958889>. 6
- [SDC*17] SENGUPTA A., DASGUPTA A., CHAUDHURI A., GEORGE A., ROURAY A., GUHA R.: A multimodal system for assessing alertness levels due to cognitive loading. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering PP* (02 2017), 1–1. doi:[10.1109/TNSRE.2017.2672080](https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2017.2672080). 2
- [SGL*14] STUART S., GALNA B., LORD S., ROCHESTER L., GODFREY A.: Quantifying saccades while walking: Validity of a novel velocity-based algorithm for mobile eye tracking. vol. 2014. doi:[10.1109/EMBC.2014.6944931](https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2014.6944931). 4
- [SM71] SHEPARD R. N., METZLER J.: Mental rotation of three-dimensional objects. *Science* 171, 3972 (1971), 701–703. 3
- [SR 25] SR RESEARCH LTD.: Eyelink 3 – eye and head tracker. <https://www.sr-research.com/eyelink-3/>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-08-12. 1
- [SRN22] SHI C., ROTHROCK L., NOAH B.: Using eye-tracking to predict cognitive workload in a control room environment. In *Human-Automation Interaction: Manufacturing, Services and User Experience*. Springer, 2022, pp. 217–233. 2
- [SSP*18] SERRANO J. P. D., SOLTEZ J. M. A., PASCUAL R. K. C., CASTILLO J. C. D., TORRES J. L., CRUZ F. R. G.: Portable stress level detector based on galvanic skin response, heart rate, and body temperature. In *2018 IEEE 10th International Conference on Humanoid, Nanotechnology, Information Technology, Communication and Control, Environment and Management (HNICEM)* (2018), pp. 1–5. doi:[10.1109/HNICEM.2018.8666352](https://doi.org/10.1109/HNICEM.2018.8666352). 1
- [SWG21] SCHWEIZER T., WYSS T., GILGEN-AMMANN R.: Detecting soldiers' fatigue using eye-tracking glasses: Practical field applications and research opportunities. *Military Medicine* 187, 11-12 (12 2021), e1330–e1337. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/milmed/usab509>, arXiv: <https://academic.oup.com/milmed/article-pdf/187/11-12/e1330/46682604/usab509.pdf>, doi: [10.1093/milmed/usab509](https://doi.org/10.1093/milmed/usab509). 2
- [SWMD25] SHAH V., WATANABE K., MOSER B. B., DENGEL A.: Pupilsense: A novel application for webcam-based pupil diameter estimation. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.11204>, arXiv:2407.11204. 2
- [SZJ*22] SHI L., ZHENG L., JIN D., LIN Z., ZHANG Q., ZHANG M.: Assessment of combination of automated pupillometry and heart rate variability to detect driving fatigue. *Frontiers in Public Health* 10 (02 2022). doi:[10.3389/fpubh.2022.828428](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.828428). 1
- [TIW14] TANAKA M., ISHII A., WATANABE Y.: Neural effects of mental fatigue caused by continuous attention load: a magnetoencephalography study. *Brain research* 1561 (2014), 60–66. 1
- [TLF03] TERRY P., LANE A., FOGARTY G.: Construct validity of the profile of mood states — adolescents for use with adults. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise* 4, 2 (2003), 125–139. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1469029201000358>, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1469-0292\(01\)00035-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1469-0292(01)00035-8). 5
- [TLLK99] TERRY P. C., LANE A. M., LANE H. J., KEOHANE L.: Development and validation of a mood measure for adolescents. *Journal of Sports Sciences* 17, 11 (1999), 861–872. PMID: 10585166. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/026404199365425>, arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1080/026404199365425>, doi:[10.1080/026404199365425](https://doi.org/10.1080/026404199365425). 5
- [Tob25] TOBII AB: Tobii eye tracking. <https://www.tobii.com/>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-08-12. 1
- [TVR*21] TSENG V. W.-S., VALLIAPPAN N., RAMACHANDRAN V., CHOUDHURY T., NAVALPAKKAM V.: Digital biomarker of mental fatigue. *npj Digital Medicine* 4, 1 (Mar. 2021), 47. doi:[10.1038/s41746-021-00415-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00415-6). 2
- [UFAV14] UNSWORTH N., FUKUDA K., AWH E., VOGEL E. K.: Working memory and fluid intelligence: Capacity, attention control, and secondary memory retrieval. *Cognitive Psychology* 71 (2014), 1–26. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010028514000140>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogpsych.2014.01.003>. 2
- [USO*23] UCHIYAMA Y., SAWAI S., OMI T., YAMAUCHI K., TAMURA K., SAKATA T., NAKAJIMA K., SAKAI H.: Convergent validity of video-based observer rating of drowsiness, against subjective, behavioral, and physiological measures. *PLoS ONE* 18, 5 (2023), e0285557. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285557>, doi:[10.1371/journal.pone.0285557](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285557). 2
- [VG96] VELTMAN J., GAILLARD A.: Physiological indices of workload in a simulated flight task. *Biological Psychology* 42, 3 (1996), 323–342. Psychophysiology of Workload. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301051195051651>, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0511\(95\)05165-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0511(95)05165-1). 1
- [WCH*24] WU S., CHEN H., HOU L., ZHANG G. K., LI C.-Q.: Using eye-tracking to measure worker situation awareness in augmented reality. *Automation in Construction* 165 (2024), 105582. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0926580524003182>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2024.105582>. 2

- [WTH*09] WEST C., TAN A., HABERMANN T., SLOAN J., SHANAFELT T.: West cp, tan ad, habermann tm, sloan ja, shanafelt td. association of resident fatigue and distress with perceived medical errors. *JAMA : the journal of the American Medical Association* 302 (09 2009), 1294–300. doi:10.1001/jama.2009.1389. 1
- [WTX*24] WANG Y., TURNBULL A., XU Y., HEFFNER K., LIN F. V., ADELI E.: Vision-based estimation of fatigue and engagement in cognitive training sessions. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 154 (2024), 102923. doi:10.1016/j.artmed.2024.102923. 2
- [XZY*25] XU F., ZHOU T., YOU H., WU J., LEDGERWOOD S., DU J.: *Cognitive Overload in Indoor Wayfinding Tasks: Correlation with Performance*. Tech. rep., SSRN, May 12 2025. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5251689> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5251689>. 2
- [YCY23] YU X., CHEN C.-H., YANG H.: Air traffic controllers' mental fatigue recognition: A multi-sensor information fusion-based deep learning approach. *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 57 (2023), 102123. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1474034623002513>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102123>. 2
- [YHJ*24] YANG H., HU N., JIA R., ZHANG X., XIE X., LIU X., CHEN N.: How does driver fatigue monitor system design affect carsharing drivers? an approach to the quantification of driver mental stress and visual attention. *Travel Behaviour and Society* 35 (2024), 100755. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214367X24000188>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2024.100755>. 2
- [YK18] YAMADA Y., KOBAYASHI M.: Detecting mental fatigue from eye-tracking data gathered while watching video: Evaluation in younger and older adults. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 91 (2018), 39–48. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0933365717306140>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2018.06.005>. 2
- [YK21] YANG X., KRAJBICH I.: Webcam-based online eye-tracking for behavioral research. *Judgment and Decision Making* 16, 6 (2021), 1485–1505. doi:10.1017/S1930297500008512. 1
- [ZGZ*23] ZHANG Y., GUO H., ZHOU Y., XU C., LIAO Y.: Recognising drivers' mental fatigue based on eeg multi-dimensional feature selection and fusion. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 79 (2023), 104237. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1746809422006917>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2022.104237>. 1
- [ZMMO*18a] ZARGARI MARANDI R., MADELEINE P., OMLAND , VUILLERME N., SAMANI A.: Eye movement characteristics reflected fatigue development in both young and elderly individuals. *Scientific Reports* 8 (09 2018). doi:10.1038/s41598-018-31577-1. 2
- [ZMMO*18b] ZARGARI MARANDI R., MADELEINE P., OMLAND , VUILLERME N., SAMANI A.: Eye movement characteristics reflected fatigue development in both young and elderly individuals. *Scientific Reports* 8, 1 (2018), 1–9. URL: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-31577-1>, doi:10.1038/s41598-018-31577-1. 2